

Supporting Information

High protein-loading silica template for heterogeneous protein crystallisation

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Section S1. Summary of materials used.

More details of the materials are summarised in the table below for readers interested in repeating the experiments.

Compound name	CAS number	Supplier	Product code	Note
Synthesis of mesoporous silica				
Pluronic P-123	9003-11-6	Sigma Aldrich	435465-250ML	Mn ~ 5800
HCl	7647-01-0	VWR	20252.335	Analytical reagent (37%)
TEOS	78-10-4	Sigma Aldrich	131903-1L	Reagent grade (98%)
Analysis of mesoporous silica				
Holey Carbon film on Copper 300 mesh	---	EM Resolutions	HC300Cu100	100
Carbon conductive adhesive tape	---	Agar Scientific	AGG3939	8mm x 20m
Ethanol	64-17-5	VWR	20821.33	Analytical reagent ($\geq 99.8\%$)
Protein crystallisation				
Lysozyme from chicken egg white	12650-88-3	Sigma Aldrich	L6876-10G	Lyophilized powder (protein $\geq 90\%$, $\geq 40,000$ units/mg protein)
Thaumatococcus daniellii	53850-34-3	Sigma Aldrich	T7638-1G	
Piperazine-1,4-bis(2-ethanesulfonic acid) (PIPES)	5625-37-6	Sigma Aldrich	P6757-100G	$\geq 99\%$ (titration)
Sodium hydroxide	1310-73-2	VWR	28244.295	Pellets (98.5 – 100.5%)
Potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate	6381-59-5	Sigma Aldrich	217255-500G	ACS reagent (99%)
Polypropylene microcentrifuge tube	---	Fisher Scientific	11558232	1.5 mL with cap

Section S2. Pore size determination of mesoporous silica.

Figure S1. Graph of BJH adsorption dA/dD pore area.

Figure S2. Graph of BJH desorption dV/dD pore volume.

Section S3. Protein concentration measurements.

The calibration curves for lysozyme and thaumatin are shown below. Both curves have high linearity over the range of protein concentration relevant in the current experiments.

Figure S3. Calibration curve for lysozyme.

Figure S4. Calibration curve for thaumatin.

Section S4. Lysozyme sorption by template

The quantities of lysozyme and thaumatin ad/absorbed onto the mesoporous silica at different protein concentrations (in solution) at 25 °C are shown below.

Figure S5. Sorption quantity of lysozyme by silica template at equilibrium (contacting fresh silica template with protein/precipitant solution; temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S6. Sorption quantity of lysozyme by silica template at the end of conditioning (contacting silica template with fresh protein/precipitant solution repeatedly; temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Section S5. Lysozyme crystallisation (initial protein concentration = 5.0 – 47.5 mg/mL)

The protein concentrations (in solution) over time are shown below. The decrease of protein concentrations was due to the formation of crystals. The protein concentrations for the seeded samples were always lower than the unseeded samples due to the faster crystallisation kinetics.

Figure S7. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 47.5 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S8. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 42.5 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S9. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 38 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S10. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 34 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S11. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 15 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S12. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 12.5 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S13. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 10 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S14. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 7.5 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Figure S15. Unseeded and seeded lysozyme crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 5 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).

Section S6. Thaumatin crystallisation (initial protein concentration = 23.0 mg/mL)

Figure S16. Unseeded and seeded thaumatin crystallisation with initial protein concentration of 23.0 mg/mL (temperature = 25 °C; potassium sodium tartrate tetrahydrate concentration = 0.5 M).